

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Effect of 5-methylsalicylic acid on deposition of chitosan coatings on AZ31 magnesium alloy and their degradation in Hank's solution

Dzmitry Kharytonau^{1*}, Viktoryia Chaprasava¹, Ewelina Jarek¹, Malgorzata Zimowska¹, Grzegorz Mordarski¹

¹*Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, Krakow, Poland*

**dmitry.kharitonov@ikifp.edu.pl*

Mg alloys are promising materials for the creation of novel types of biomedical devices. In particular, they are actively examined to be used in biodegradable temporary implant applications. This concept assumes that the metal element placed into the human body will gradually degrade in time, replaced by the natural bone tissue. However, to be suitable for such applications, it is important to adjust the corrosion rate of Mg alloys in order to exclude excessive hydrogen release volumes, especially at the initial timeframes, and to prevent preliminary failure of the implant. To do so, it is possible to tailor the composition of the alloy or to perform the surface functionalization. The latter approach provides wider possibilities to modify the functional parameters of the surfaces, including improved antibacterial properties, biocompatibility, and osteointegration.

The application of natural polymer coatings is one of the possible ways to perform such a surface modification. Among them, chitosan coatings are considered very promising for biomedical applications. Chitosan, a natural polysaccharide, has very good biocompatibility, and its application can also tailor the degradation profile and antibacterial properties of the surface. At the same time, classical electrophoretic deposition of chitosan on Mg alloys results in very defective coatings due to the release of hydrogen, and additional modification of the deposition approaches is necessary.

The main aim of the present presentation is to develop a modified coordination-based deposition of chitosan coating on the surface of AZ31 Mg alloy. As a coordination agent, 5-methylsalicylic acid was used. The use of this acid also affects the antibacterial properties of the formed coatings. The deposition of the coatings was performed from aqueous solutions containing 50% of ethanol and chitosan of low, medium, and high molecular weight. Different current regimes and deposition times were tested. Characterization of the coatings included scanning electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, and Raman spectroscopy. The results confirmed the successful coordination of chitosan with 5-methylsalicylic acid. Evaluation of the corrosion degradation of samples included short- and long-term experiments. The dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used to address the initial stages of corrosion in Hank's solution, while classical impedance measurements were utilized for long-term 14-day monitoring.

The results showed that coordination with 5-methylsalicylic acid significantly improved corrosion resistance of the formed coatings and allowed for an increase in their antibacterial properties. The coatings were stable for 14 days, allowing to realization of the concept of biocompatibility and improved biodegradation and making them promising for further stages of commercialization.

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